

Complex Compounds of Substituted Thioureas. Part I. Copper Derivatives of *N*-Acetylthiourea, *S*-Acetylthiourea and *N*-Phenylthiourea

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Several complex compounds of *N*-acetyl-, *S*-acetyl-, and *N*-phenyl-thioureas with copper salts have been prepared and their properties studied.

Addition compounds of thiourea with metallic salts have been studied from very early times, notably by Maly, Claus, Rathke, Rosenheim, Kohlschutter and others (Beilstein, "Handbuch der organischen Chemie", 1921, Band III, syst. No. 216, p. 185). Little work has, however, been done till now on the compounds of substituted thioureas with metallic salts and only studies in this direction appear to be the following.

(1) $\text{CuCl} \cdot 3\text{PhTh} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Rathke, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 297).

(2) $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{AcTh}$ (Seidler, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1880, ii, 21, 140).

(3) Several compounds of ethylenethiourea with metallic ions, viz., Cu^+ , Ag^+ , Au^+ , Pd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} , (Morgan and Burstall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 143).

(4) Several copper compounds with thiourea and substituted thiourea in which copper has been represented as bivalent (Dehn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 3189).

(5) $\text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{PhTh}$; $\text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{PhTh}$; $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{PhTh}$; $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 3\text{PhTh}$ (Sahasrabudhey and Krall, this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 25).

(*N.* B. PhTh and AcTh stands for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ respectively).

It will be seen that in the metal-thiourea complexes, any particular metal ion shows a great diversity in the co-ordination number and in many cases fractional molecules of thioureas per metal ion are present. For example, in the case of copper, nine classes of thiourea complexes have been reported (including the present work), viz., (1) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:4$ (Morgan and Burstall, *loc. cit.*); (2) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:3$ (Rathke, *loc. cit.*); (3) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:2.5$ (Kohlschutter and Brintlebank, *loc. cit.*); (4) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:2.33$ (Kohlschutter, *loc. cit.*); (5) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:2.2$ (Kohlschutter *et al.*, *loc. cit.*); (6) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:2$ (Kohlschutter *et al.*, *loc. cit.*); (7) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:1.75$ (present work); (8) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:1.5$ (present work); (9) $\text{M}:\text{RTh}=1:1$ (Rathke, *loc. cit.*).

Of these nine types, a few compounds of the types (1), (2), (3), (6), (7), (8), and (9) have been obtained in the present work. Types (2), (6), and (9) can be taken as definite compounds and not mixtures, as a large number of compounds of each of the types (2) and (6) can be obtained in various ways, and as type (9) has the lowest thiourea content. The only compound of the type (1) $\text{CuNO}_3 \cdot 4$ ethylenethiourea (Morgan and Burstall, *loc. cit.*)

seems to be a definite compound since it has been prepared by recrystallisation and it melts sharply at 140° . The compound Cu_2O , 8PhTh , described in this paper, is also of type (1) in which the copper atom has a co-ordination number of four. The compound 2CuCl , 5PhTh of type (3), obtained in the present work, seems to be a definite compound as various other compounds of this type have been prepared by early workers in different experimental conditions. Compounds 2CuCl , 3Th ; 2CuCl , 3AcTh ; 2CuCl , 3PhTh of type (8) have been described in the present paper. Compound 2CuCl , 3AcTh has been prepared under two different experimental conditions and hence it may be regarded as a definite compound. The two other compounds, 2CuCl , 3Th and 2CuCl , 3PhTh were also obtained by two analogous methods. The compound 4CuCl , 7AcTh , the only member of type (7), has been obtained by one experimental condition only and therefore it is difficult to judge whether it is a compound or a mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Derivatives of N-Acetylthiourca

N-Acetylthiourca was prepared by the method of Neucki (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 599), m.p. 165° . (Found: N, 23.68. $\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNSNH}_2$ requires N, 23.73%).

Tetrakis-(N-acetylthiourca)-di-copper(I) Sulphate.—To an ice-cold solution of *N*-acetylthiourca (10 g.) in aqueous ammonia (1:3; 200 c.c.) was added an ice-cold solution of copper sulphate (5 g. in 50 c.c.) slowly with stirring at a temperature of 0° - 10° . The yellow-red precipitate formed was filtered quickly, washed successively with ice-water, cold ethanol, and ether and analysed after air drying. (Found: Cu, 18.28; N, 15.82; total S, 22.81, 22.12, 23.07; SO_4 , 13.24. Cu_2SO_4 , $4\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 18.27; N, 16.11; total S, 23.04; SO_4 , 13.81%).

The compound is feebly paramagnetic ($\mu_B \approx 0.33$ B.M.), the moment value being abnormally low for copper (II). It seems that the substance is a mixture of the copper (I) compound (A) and copper (II) compound (B), which differ only by two H-atoms and there is but little difference in their analytical compositions.

(where, AcT stands for $\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNH}$)

Arguments in favour of the bridging property of thiourea molecule through the linkage of the S-atom in it to two metal atoms by two co-ordinate bonds have been adduced in Part II of this paper (this issue, p. 765).

The substance turns black on slight warming (40°) or on keeping in a vacuum desiccator. It keeps well for nearly one day in air. With HCl (dilute) it turns white with the liberation of H_2S . With NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, or ether.

Tris-(thiourea)-di-copper(I) Chloride.—The preceding substance (5 g.) was rubbed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with HCl (1:1; 25 c.c.) in a mortar, cooled in ice, until colour of the substance became milky white; the mixture was then filtered, washed successively with ice-cold water and cold ethanol. It was dried in air and analysed. (Found: Cu, 29.17; N, 19.2; Cl, 17.01. $2CuCl$, $?NH_2CSNH_2$ requires Cu, 29.81; N, 19.71; Cl, 16.66%). Analysis shows that the acetyl group in *N*-acetylthiourea has been lost, evidently through hydrolysis caused by the strong hydrochloric acid.

The compound is highly stable and insoluble in HCl. (conc.). With NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in ether, acetone, ethanol, or water and is diamagnetic.

Heptakis-(N-acetylthiourea)-tetra-copper(I) Chloride.—Hydrated cupric chloride (1g.) in water (10 c.c.) was added slowly with stirring to a solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (3.5 g.) in 120 c. c. of aqueous acetone (1:4) at the room temperature; the yellowish white precipitate thus formed was filtered and washed successively with water, ethanol, and ether. It was dried in air and analysed. (Found: Cu, 20.87; N, 15.59; Cl, 12.30. $4CuCl$, $7C_2H_5CONHC_2H_4NH_2$ requires Cu, 20.79; N, 16.03; Cl, 11.82%).

The compound is stable and decomposes with NaOH solution, forming a red substance which changes to a black one. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, ether, or acetone and is diamagnetic.

Tris-(N-acetylthiourea)-di-copper(I) Chloride.—A solution of anhydrous cupric chloride (1g.) in dry anhydrous acetone (80 c.c.) was added dropwise to a solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (molecular proportion, 1:2; 1.7g) in anhydrous acetone (60 c.c.). A transient red colour appeared which vanished forming a yellow precipitate. The mixture was heated for 5 minutes on a water bath with stirring when the supernatant liquid became colorless. It was then cooled, filtered, and washed with acetone till free of cupric chloride. It was dried in air and analysed. (Found: Cu, 23.24; N, 15.53; Cl, 12.25. $2CuCl$, $3C_2H_5CONHC_2H_4NH_2$ requires Cu, 23.00; N, 15.21; Cl, 12.86%).

The same compound was obtained when cupric chloride and *N*-acetylthiourea in molecular proportion (1:1) were used for the preparation.

The compound is stable. With NaOH it turns first red and then black. It is insoluble in water, acetone, or ether and is paramagnetic giving a moment value of 0.26 B.M. It indicates the presence of some copper(II) in the product.

Acid Hydrochloride of Bis-(thiourea)-copper(I) Chloride.—To *N*-acetylthiourea (2.5g.) in 150 c.c. of water was added slowly cuprous chloride (1g., prepared by the method of Daniel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **37**, 1167) in HCl solution (1:1, 4 c.c.), when a white precipitate was formed which was filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol, and ether. It was dried and analysed. (Found: Cu, 21.34; N, 18.93; Cl, 24.20. $CuCl$, $2NH_2CSNH_2$, HCl requires Cu, 22.11; N, 19.48; Cl, 24.66%).

The compound is diamagnetic. The acetyl group in *N*-acetylthiourea has evidently been removed by hydrolysis caused by strong hydrochloric acid.

The substance is stable and insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. With NaOH it turns black. It is insoluble in water, alcohol, or ether.

Uni-(N-acetylthiourea)-copper Hydroxide.—Copper sulphate (1.75 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was mixed with sodium potassium tartrate (1.75 g.) and NaOH (0.7 g.) in 5 c.c. of water and the mixture was cooled in ice. A saturated solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (7 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.) at about 0° was added with stirring into the above ice-cold solution, when a red precipitate was formed which was filtered rapidly and washed successively with ice-cold water and cold acetone. It was dried in vacuum at about 10° (without the use of desiccating agent) and analysed. [Found: Cu, 30.80; N, 13.91. (I) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2, \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 29.5; N, 12.99; (II) $\text{CuOH}, \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2, \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 30.62; N, 13.51; (III) $\text{Cu}(-\text{OH})-\text{SC}(=\text{NH})\text{NHCONH}_2, \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 30.68; N, 13.54%]. The analytical results rule out formula (I), but cannot decide between formulas (II) and (III).

The compound is stable at ordinary temperature when dry; with NaOH at room temperature it turns red and then black. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, or acetone and is paramagnetic, with a B. M. value of 0.85 per copper atom. The value suggests an admixture of copper (I) and copper (II) compounds of formulas (II) and (III).

Copper Derivatives of S-Acetylthiourea

S-Acetylthiourea was prepared by the method of Dixon and Howthorne (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 97, 122). [Found: N, 23.29. Calc. for $\text{CH}_3\text{COSC}(=\text{NH})\text{NH}_2$: N, 23.72%]. The substance is deliquescent and its m.p. 109° coincides with that of $\text{NH}_2-\text{C}(=\text{NH})-\text{S}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3\cdot\text{HCl}$, described by Dixon and Howthorne (*loc. cit.*) It is highly soluble and it easily hydrolyses to thiourea and acetic acid. It has comparatively a low solubility in anhydrous acetone or in freshly distilled absolute ethanol, but it is soluble in glacial acetic acid. Its molecular formula has been described by Dixon and Howthorne (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1907, 1109) to be $\text{NH}_2-\text{C}(=\text{NH})=\text{S}-\text{COCH}_3\cdot\text{HCl}$, but in our experimental condition (vacuum desiccation) 'HCl' molecule of the substance is gradually lost until at last $\text{H}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{C}(=\text{NH})\cdot\text{S}-\text{COCH}_3$ only remains.

Uni-(S-acetylthiourea)-copper (I) Chloride.—When an aqueous solution of cupric chloride (1 g.) was mixed with an aqueous solution of *S*-acetylthiourea, a white spongy precipitate was formed, which was found to be uni-thiourea-copper (I) chloride, described by Rosenheim and Loewenstamm (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 24, 66). Evidently *S*-acetylthiourea hydrolyses with water giving thiourea which forms the complex with copper. The same compound was obtained in slightly aqueous acetone as well. *S*-Acetylthiourea therefore hydrolyses in contact with even a very small amount of water present in the acetone. Use of glacial acetic acid also gave no better results, but formed a mixture of $\text{CuCl}, 2\text{NH}_2\text{CSNH}_2, \text{HCl}$ and $\text{CuCl}, 2\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2, \text{HCl}$. Finally, a dilute solution of freshly prepared *S*-acetylthiourea in freshly distilled (over silica gel) anhydrous acetone was mixed with a solution of anhydrous cupric chloride (heating $\text{CuCl}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for 2 hours at 140° in an air oven) in anhydrous acetone, when a white precipitate was formed, which was rapidly filtered, washed with anhydrous acetone, dried at 10° in a desiccator, and analysed after one day. (Found: Cu, 29.63; N, 13.14; Cl, 16.71. $\text{CuCl}, \text{CH}_3\text{COSC}(=\text{NH})\text{NH}_2$

requires Cu, 23.26; N, 12.91; Cl, 16.33%). The compound appears to be fairly stable at room temperature and decomposes near 100° or by alkali solution. It is soluble in water, acetone, or ethanol.

Copper Derivatives of N-Phenylthiourea

N-Phenylthiourea was prepared by the method of De Clermont (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 146), m. p., 154°. (Found: N, 18.38. Calc. for $C_6H_5NHCSNH_2$: N, 18.40%). It is very little soluble in water, but highly soluble in ether, acetone, or ethanol and is quite stable. Its solubility in water is just a little more than 1% at room temperature (32-33°).

Uni-(N-phenylthiourea)-copper Chloride.—An ice-cold concentrated solution of anhydrous cupric chloride (2 g.) in absolute ethanol was added slowly with stirring to an ice-cold solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (4.6 g.) in the same medium, when a white precipitate was formed, which was filtered, washed, dried at 10°, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 25.12; N, 11.27; Cl, 14.71. $CuCl, C_6H_5NHCSNH_2$ requires Cu, 25.30; N, 11.15; Cl, 14.14%.)

The compound is yellowish white and stable. With NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in ethanol, but soluble in acetone and is paramagnetic, with μ_B (eff.) = 0.64 B.M., which indicates the presence of some copper (II), presumably as the compound $Cu(-Cl)-SC(=NH)NHC_6H_5$.

Pentakis-(N-phenylthiourea)-di-copper (I) Chloride.—An aqueous solution of cupric chloride hydrate (1 g.) was added with stirring to an aqueous solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (3.5 g.), when a white precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol, and acetone, and analysed when dry. (Found: Cu, 13.48; N, 15.04; Cl, 7.71; S, 16.55. $2 CuCl, 5C_6H_5NHCSNH_2$ requires Cu, 13.25; N, 14.60; Cl, 7.40; S, 16.70%.)

The compound is very stable. An aqueous suspension of the substance does not change in colour even at 100°. With dilute NaOH solution it turns black. It is slightly soluble in water but not in ethanol or acetone. It is diamagnetic.

Hexakis-(N-phenylthiourea)-di-copper(I) Sulphate.—An aqueous solution of copper sulphate (2 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (6 g.) when a white precipitate was formed, which was filtered, washed with water and acetone, dried at 10°, and analysed. (Found: Cu, 10.97; N, 14.57; total S, 18.60, 19.90, 19.84. $Cu_2SO_4, 6C_6H_5NHCSNH_2$ requires Cu, 11.2; N, 14.8; total S, 19.73%.)

The substance is yellow and stable. Its aqueous suspension on boiling does not change in colour. With NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in water and fairly soluble in acetone but highly soluble in ether. It is diamagnetic.

Bis-(N-phenylthiourea)-copper(I) Hydroxide.—Copper sulphate (1 g.) in ice-cold water (25 c.c.) was added slowly to an ice-cold solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (6 g.) in a mixture of 250 c.c. of water, 230 c.c. of liquor ammonia and 20 c.c. of ethanol, when a brown precipitate was formed, which was filtered as usual. (Found: Cu, 16.91; N, 14.62; S, 15.70. $CuOH, 2C_6H_5NHCSNH_2$ requires Cu, 16.51; N, 14.56; S, 16.64%). The compound shows a very low magnetic moment [μ_B (eff.) = 0.16 B.M.] indicating presence of some copper (II)

The compound is moderately stable and decomposes by HCl (dil.) or by NaOH (dil.). It is insoluble in water or ethanol but soluble in acetone.

Tris-(N-phenylthiourea)-di-copper Chloride.—Bis-(*N*-phenylthiourea)-copper(I) hydroxide, prepared as above, was rubbed in a mortar with hydrochloric acid solution (1:1) when the brown compound was transformed into a white one, which was treated as usual. (Found: Cu, 19.52; N, 12.05; Cl, 11.17. $2\text{CuCl}, 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 19.40; N, 12.84; Cl, 10.87%.)

The compound is highly stable and insoluble in HCl (conc.). It turns black with NaOH solution on boiling. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, or acetone. It is paramagnetic with μ_B (eff.) = 0.42 B.M., suggesting the presence of some copper (II) in form of the compound shown below.

Octakis-(N-phenylthiourea)-di-copper (I) Oxide.—The preparation of the two compounds $\text{NH}_2\text{CSNH}_2, \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2, \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, described by Dehn (*loc. cit.*), was attempted in the present work following the method of the former; but none of the compounds could be isolated. In the first case, a grass-green precipitate, claimed by Dehn to be $\text{NH}_2\text{CSNH}_2, \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, was formed at 0° , but during filtration at room temperature of about 30° , it turned black, being changed to insoluble copper sulphide. In an attempt to prepare the yellow compound, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2, \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, a solution containing 1.75g. of Rochelle salt, 0.7g. of sodium hydroxide in 5 c.c. water, and 1.75 g. of copper sulphate in 10 c. c. of water was added to an ice-cold, saturated solution of *N*-phenylthiourea in acetone, when a beautiful green compound containing no nitrogen or sulphur was obtained. In a subsequent attempt an excess of ice-cold water was added to the well-cooled mixture of "Fehling solution" and acetone solution of *N*-phenylthiourea, when a yellow compound was precipitated, which was filtered, washed with ice-cold water, dried in a vacuum desiccator at 10° , and analysed. (Found: Cu, 9.42; N, 17.4; S, 18.95. $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}, 8\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ requires Cu, 9.35; N, 16.50; S, 18.86%.)

The compound is moderately stable. With NaOH solution it turns black on boiling. It is insoluble in water, but soluble in acetone or ether. The corrected value of the atomic susceptibility for Cu has been found to be $+4.7 \times 10^{-6}$ at 31° ; the feeble paramagnetism might be due to impurities. The magnetic susceptibilities of most of the compounds obtained were measured by a Gouy balance in a maximum field strength of 9.36×10^3 gauss and a current strength of 5 amperes. The values of μ_B (eff.) have been calculated by applying the air correction and the diamagnetic correction.

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